

D6.4: Draft Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (draft PDER)

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CHANGE CONTROL

Date	Version	Author (Company)	Changes to document
27/03/2019	v01.0	SONACA	Initial version
08/04/2019	V01.1	Cranfield University	Inputs from CU
08/04/2019	V01.2	Selectarc	Inputs from Selectarc
19/04/2019	V01.3	UAC	Inputs from UAC
17/06/2019	V01.4	IK4 LORTEK	Revised by Topic Manager
05/07/2019	V01.5	SONACA	Implementation of comments
15/07/2019	V01.6	IK4 LORTEK	Approved
28/01/2021	V02.0	SONACA	Rework of the document following Cleansky's feedback

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1. Introduction

IAWAS was launched:

- To deliver new wire compositions allowing the Laser Beam Welding (LBW) of Al-Cu-Li alloys and the Wire Arc Additive Manufacturing (WAAM) of Li containing aluminium alloys.
- To develop WAAM process for Li containing aluminium alloys
- To develop the LBW process
- To manufacture a demonstrator with WAAM technology

The highest intended Technology Readiness Level (TRL) is for the wire to be manufactured with the new composition. Indeed, at the end of the project, IAWAS initial goal was to reach TRL 9 and to have a product ready to be commercialized. This initial targeted TRL might be reduced with the encountered difficulties with the wire production. However, UAC will be able to cast and extrude the material, and the production unit of Selectarc Welding, commonly used for the current commercial filler wires, will be adjusted to produce this new filler wire.

The material issued from this work will allow IAWAS to propose a finished product able to merge the AM advantages with the desirable properties of Li containing aluminium alloys (low density, excellent corrosion resistance, superior fatigue performance compared to other Al alloys, high fracture toughness, and excellent static properties).

With these new products IAWAS aims at luring as many industrial sectors as possible. Nevertheless, due to the current high price of Li and other elements susceptible to be added to the composition (i.e. Sc or Ag) and to the complex manufacturing route of Li containing aluminium alloys, its price at the moment, could be well over the average price of a "common" filler wire. That is why, after potential further development of the extrusion and drawing processes, the first expected users are likely to belong to the Aeronautic or Aerospace field, in which SONACA with its extended expertise can play an important role transmitting IAWAS results and looking into possible applications for its implementation.

It is foreseen WAAM process at Cranfield University will achieve TRL 5 for Li containing aluminium alloys. A new hybrid WAAM process will be designed and validated by the manufacturing of a demonstrator to be used by ecoTECH (discussions are being held in order to fix the geometry and dimensions of this demonstrator). As Cranfield University is a University and a research center, the intention is to incorporate IAWAS outputs in all their current existing trainings and projects related to WAAM.

The level of readiness of the LBW of Al-Cu-Li sheets will be of TRL 3. The goal of the development of this process is to prove in a sample scale that this welding is possible and that the main problems, already identified in the literature review, are solved with the use of the new wire and the optimization of the parameters. The direct end user of this output will be Lortek, for the demonstrator of ecoTECH project in which some fuselage panels of Al-Cu-Li alloy will be welded. In order to help as much as possible this task, IAWAS approach will try to get closer to ecoTECH configuration (conventional laser technology instead of the hybrid one, same materials to be welded will be used...).

2. Dissemination plan and exploitation of results

IAWAS aims at exploiting the project results as much as possible as it is in the interest of all partners to disseminate the work to be developed in this project (always respecting the IPR and the signed Grant Agreement). The partnership involves companies that have the opportunity to offer future products, mainly the different developed alloys for UAC and the drawn wires for Selectarc. Cranfield University and SONACA will have research and industrialization roles that offer the necessary consultancy and engineering in order for the products to be successfully commercialised and applied.

Information about the study shall be addressed to the largest number of potentially interested parties. In this way, several types of audiences will be considered for the exploitation and dissemination activities:

- General public.
- End users: suitable Al alloy filler wire compositions and process implementations that solve the current issues in the WAAM and LBW of Li-containing Al alloys.
- Aeronautical community: the potential of the WAAM process for the manufacturing of complex parts made of new Al alloys and the potential of the LBW as an alternative to the traditional mechanical fastening for the assembly of new Al alloy parts.

This deliverable aims at defining the way in which each of the four IAWAS partners shall communicate and deliver their work. As a reminder, here there is an extract of the signed GA reflecting some important points to take into consideration:

“Unless it goes against their legitimate interests, each beneficiary must — as soon as possible — ‘disseminate’ its results by disclosing them to the public by appropriate means (other than those resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including in scientific publications (in any medium).

Each beneficiary must — up to four years after the period set out in Article 3 — take measures aiming to ensure ‘exploitation’ of its results (either directly or indirectly, in particular through transfer or licensing; see Article 30) by:

- (a) using them in further research activities (outside the action);
- (b) developing, creating or marketing a product or process;
- (c) creating and providing a service, or
- (d) using them in standardisation activities.

Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

In particular, it must:

- (a) as soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications;

Moreover, the beneficiary must aim to deposit at the same time the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications.

- (b) ensure open access to the deposited publication — via the repository — at the latest:

(i) on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or

(ii) within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities) in any other case.

(c) ensure open access — via the repository — to the bibliographic metadata that identify the deposited publication.

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- the terms “Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking”, “European Union (EU)” and “Horizon 2020”;
- the visual requirements: Clean Sky 2 Joint Undertaking logo, European Union emblem, logo of the project and specific acknowledgement.
- the name of the action, acronym and grant number;
- the publication date, and length of embargo period if applicable, and
- a persistent identifier.””

All partners will contribute to the tasks of dissemination and specifically by participating to international conferences, promoting standardization efforts and publishing in established journals.

They have also contributed to the writing of “D6.4: Draft Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (draft PDER)” and they will do the same for the writing of “D6.5: Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PDER)”.

2.1. Exploitation of results during the 2018-2020 period

Based on the activities performed in this period and the reporting related to the IAWAS project, both UACE and SelectArc have mainly further developed their knowledge on:

- the production (casting, extrusion and/or wire drawing) of Aluminium-Lithium alloys. New process modifications have been performed in order to enable the production of these wires.
- improved wire compositions for WAAM and LBW applications

Based on the activities performed in this period and the reporting related to the IAWAS project, Sonaca and CRM have mainly further developed their knowledge on the laser beam welding of aluminium alloys (with an without Lithium) on Al-Li substrates including the effect of the process parameters and basic mechanical properties.

Based on the activities performed in this period and the reporting related to the IAWAS project, Cranfield University has mainly further developed its knowledge on the WAAM of Aluminium-Lithium alloys (mainly Al-2%Li and 2395 alloys) including the influence of the process parameters.

2.2. Communication actions during the 2018-2020 period

- I. Internal communication (between the IAWAS partners)
 - a. Sharepoint

A SharePoint site has been created and is accessible to all partners and to the Topic Managers in order to improve the communication between the partners and to make all IAWAS activities well known by the other partners.

The site is divided in various sections:

- Calendar: the upcoming milestones, deliverables due dates and meetings are highlighted.
- Literature review: scientific articles related to the different tasks are uploaded to make them available to all participants.
- Meeting documents: all MoM and presentations used during meetings are available inside this folder.
- Administrative documents and deliverables: All deliverables (official deliverables and intermediated reports) have to be saved here.
- Photos: when it is possible to illustrate the achievements or the progress of the activities the images are shared in this folder.
- Tasks: Tasks are identified in a list with the due date and the person responsible for its completion.

Figure 1 IAWAS SharePoint

- b. Bimonthly meetings

During this period, IAWAS held bimonthly teleconferences that gathered all partners, the Topic Managers and other members of EcoTECH. During the meeting the project progress was presented by each company and comments of the topic manager on deliverables and future tasks were reviewed.

- II. External communications

Communications regarding the IAWAS project and specific milestones have been posted as:

- news on partners websites
- news on LinkedIn

Figure 2 presents the first LinkedIn post concerning the start of the IAWAS project, published by Sonaca Engineering Services.

Sonaca Engineering Services 506 followers 3mo

Innovative Aluminium filler Wires for Aircraft Structures
IAWAS kick-off meeting was successfully held at SONACA's premises (B) on October 2nd.

Sonaca, as project coordinator and core partners, [Universal Alloy Corporation Europe Dumbavita](#), [SELECTARC WELDING & BRAZING](#), [Cranfield University](#), with the support of the Topic manager, [IK4-LORTEK](#), defined the first actions to be carried out.

The first goal of the project is to develop a filler wire to be used in the WAAM and LBW of 3rd generation Al-Li alloys. As a first step, works are focused on the review of studies already performed in the field. The manufacturing of the first wires with existing extrudable Al alloys has also started.

The definition of the first new wire composition is expected at the very beginning of next year!

In this multidisciplinary consortium, Sonaca's expertise will contribute to the requirements definition and the optimization of the LBW process. The manufacturing and testing of the LBW coupons made with different wires will allow us to select the ones with the best properties and to identify where the improvements might come from.

Stay tuned on https://lnkd.in/dyN_QMn

#H2020-CS2 #IAWAS #Sonaca_Services #Material&Process-Expertise #ServingYourFuture...Now!

Figure 2 First LinkedIn communication regarding IAWAS KOM

2.3. Dissemination actions during the 2018-2020 period

During this period, IAWAS partners attended several workshops and conferences. Table 1 lists the events in which IAWAS partners have participated.

Table 1 Workshops and events

No.	Type of activities	Main leader	Title	Date/Period	Place	Type of audience	Size of audience	Permanent identifiers ISBN	Countries addressed
1	Workshop	Sonaca	CS2 Workshop on AM in Aviation	23-24 January 2019	Aachen (Fraunhofer Institute for Laser Technology ILT)	Industry	Unknown	/	EU level
2	Conference	Cranfield University	3rd International Conference on Light Materials (LightMat)	5-7 November 2019	Manchester (Manchester Conference Centre)	Scientific community	~150	/	International level
3	Workshop	Cranfield University	WAAMMat day	4 December 2019	Cranfield (Cranfield University)	Industry & Scientific community	~60	/	International level
4	Conference	Cranfield University	Materials Science and Technology of Additive Manufacturing Conference & Exhibition (MSTAM)	11 December 2019	Bremen (University of Bremen)	Scientific community	~80	/	International level
5	Conference	Cranfield University	International Conference on Aluminium Alloys (ICAA17)	25-29 October 2020	Grenoble (Grenoble institute of Technology)	Scientific community	~250	/	International level
6	Workshop	Cranfield University	NEWAM dissemination day	12 November 2020	Online	Industry & Scientific community	~60	/	International level

Beside these workshops and conferences, metal additive manufacture is already taught on various MSc course at Cranfield University. The outputs from IAWAS are used to update and inform these teachings, as well as feed directly into the ADMIRE project (which is setting up of MSc on Metal AM).